

AUDIO-VISUAL SCENES REPOSITORY: HOW TO USE THE PROVIDED ENVIRONMENTS

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This document gives a short introduction on how to use the Audio-Visual environments provided in this file repository. First of all you will note that there are three environments to be found:

- Living room
- Pub
- Underground station

Each of them is provided in a separate directory. Within each directory, you will find a word document that first of all describes the properties of the respective environment, such that you can judge whether the Audio-Visual environment is interesting for your research. A detailed description of the materials that are provided can be seen there:

- A visual model
- An acoustical model
- A range of acoustic measurements that allow you to set up a specific scenario, allowing for specific acoustic rendering configurations; for example, for a number of source-receiver combinations, room impulse responses and binaural room impulse responses are provided.

The Audio-Visual models are provided in .obj format, and are accompanied by visual texture files and acoustic material properties. In this document you will find some guide lines for using the .obj files in your rendering methods.

Link to the repository: https://zenodo.org/communities/audiovisual_scenes/

1 CHECKING-LIST OF MODEL INFORMATION

The environments downloaded from the database need to fulfil a list of requirements in order to assure repeatability in the implementation procedures among users. For this reason, the left column of the following table contains a list of check points. They are ordered in a chronological way, according to the implementation workflows. For each of the three scenes, there are is an acoustic and a visual model. The user may want to check if their implemented model fulfils the following table to assure the repeatability in the implementation procedure.

	LIVING ROOM		PUB		UNDERGROUND	
	Acoustic Model	Visual Model	Acoustic Model	Visual Model	Acoustic Model	Visual Model
Origin reference point	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
XYZ orientation (Z-up)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	-
Normal face of surfaces looking inwards	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Material Id included	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Visual textures included	NOT NEEDED	YES	NOT NEEDED	YES	NOT NEEDED	YES
Receiver location and direction (see attachment for convention)	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES
Source location and direction	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

2 HOW TO SET-UP ONE VISUAL ENVIRONMENT

1. Download the model you wish to represent.
1. Import the OBJ file into the modelling software, such as Blender or 3ds Max.
2. Follow the “Useful export workflows”.
3. Open your Virtual Reality software, such as Unreal Engine or Unity 3D.
4. Import the exported file obtained in step 4.
5. Check that the acoustic model and the visual model are coincident in position, orientation and size.
6. Navigate inside the environment.

3 HOW TO SET-UP ONE ACOUSTIC ENVIRONMENT

1. Download the acoustic model you wish to represent.
1. Import the OBJ file into the acoustic virtual reality software, such as Raven or Razer.
2. Include the acoustic material definitions provided by the database.
3. Check that the acoustic model and the visual model are coincident in position, orientation and size.
4. Navigate inside the environment.

4 USEFUL EXPORT WORKFLOWS

The models format available in the database is .OBJ. In order to facilitate the use of the models, the following importing options have been checked, and they assure a correct importation process:

1. Import the OBJ model into **SketchUp 2022**, through “TIG: Import OBJ with Materials” plugin (free license) > Export the model to FBX format in **SketchUp 2022** > Import the FBX model to **Unreal Engine 4**.
2. Import the OBJ model into **SketchUp 2022**, through “SimLab” plugin (commercial license, valid for 30 exports in 1 month) > Export the model to FBX format in **SketchUp 2022** > Import the FBX model to **Unreal Engine 4**.
3. Import the OBJ model into **Rhinoceros 3D** (trial license, valid during 90 days) > Export the model to FBX format in **Rhinoceros 3D** > Import the FBX model to **Unreal Engine 4**.
4. Import the OBJ model into **Blender** (free license) > Export the model to FBX format from **Blender** > Import the model to **Unreal Engine 4**.
5. Open the OBJ file in the **Notepad** TXT editor (free and included in Windows) and delete the loose lines by searching the “\n” (Line) rows > Save the file as **OBJ** format > Import the OBJ file into **3ds Max** > Export the model to FBX format from **3ds Max** > Import the model to **Unreal Engine 4**.
6. Export the model with **Datasmith** from **Blender** to **Unreal Engine 4**.

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